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Table of Contents

1	<i>Introduction</i>	3
2	<i>Methodology</i>	3
3	<i>Contents of the Questionnaires</i>	4
	Questionnaire for NAPCs	4
	Questionnaire for National Funding Agencies and Stakeholders.....	4
4	<i>Results and Analysis</i>	5
	Answers from NAPCs	5
	Answers from National Funding Agencies and Stakeholders.....	6
	Analysis of the Current Situation in Europe	7
	The Italian National Access Support Programme within ITINERIS.....	7
5	<i>Summary and Conclusions</i>	8
	<i>Annex 1: Questionnaire for National Access Contact Persons (NAPCs)</i>	9
	<i>Annex 2: Answers from National Access Contact Persons (NAPCs)</i>	10
	<i>Annex 3: Questionnaire for National Funding Agencies and Stakeholders</i>	27
	<i>Annex 4: Answers from National Funding Agencies and Stakeholders</i>	33

1 Introduction

One of the objectives of ATMO-ACCESS is to identify the most suitable conditions for establishing sustainable access procedures for distributed atmospheric research infrastructures (RIs) across the EU. The goal is to define clear procedures and mechanisms for using the research facilities and benefitting from their capabilities. In the past, users mostly relied on EU funding, in particular via the INFRAIA Trans-National Access (TNA) tool, for financing physical, remote, and hybrid access to European atmospheric facilities. In the future, more sustainable solutions and co-funding options are needed for widening access opportunities (including TNA as well as virtual access, VA) and guaranteeing continuous, long-term access for all national and international user groups. Therefore, the engagement of national and international stakeholders is required.

ATMO-ACCESS WP3 approaches this issue by creating connections and then consulting key stakeholders at national and international level, with the aim to investigate potential methods and modalities for the co-funding of access programs. Task 2 of the work package is dedicated to establishing links to national stakeholders and funders and to explore possible pathways to integrate them into specific programs with the RIs, which could ensure the long-term engagement of the partners in making TNA sustainable beyond the EU funding.

The aim of this deliverable is to provide a summary of all efforts and results that have been achieved over the past three years. Material collected from 14 European countries is presented, and an analysis of the current situation is given. Potential advanced access modalities are discussed, and first examples of their implementation are shown.

2 Methodology

Liaising with national stakeholders in as many countries as possible to analyze best options for additional access modalities to RI facilities has proven to be challenging. Therefore, a stepwise approach was chosen for this task.

In a first step, the National Access Provision Coordinators (NAPCs) of ATMO-ACCESS, which are in most cases identical with the ACTRIS National Contact Persons (NCPs), have been identified and contacted. They were asked to provide a list of national stakeholders and major funding agencies that could be asked to contribute to the discussion. The information was documented in [*MS9: Documented connection established with the key national funding agencies, ministries and RPOs in Europe.*](#)

Next, the NAPCs were requested to summarize the situation in their countries from their own point of view. In a first round, seven target countries (Finland, France, Germany, Czech Republic,

Poland, Austria, and UK) had been selected for this purpose, based on the fact that they offer a variety of different funding options for national and international researchers and thus allow for case studies across Europe. The results of this survey were presented in [MS10: Draft on potential advanced access modalities based on interactions with the national stakeholders](#).

In the final and most comprehensive step, the study was opened to all countries participating in ATMO-ACCESS. All NAPCs were requested to contribute to the analysis by providing their own point of view and by contacting their national stakeholders and funding agencies and ask them for feedback on their positions and strategies regarding the support of access to RIs for national and international users and their opinion on respective co-funding modalities. Feedback from 14 NAPCs and 6 national stakeholders and funding agencies was received. A first analysis of this feedback has been given in [D3.1: Feedback document on access modalities from the perspective of the national stakeholders](#). The present deliverable provides the full documentation of the survey and a further analysis of the results.

3 Contents of the Questionnaires

For the purpose of the study, two questionnaires were developed. The first one was dedicated to the NAPCs and asked for an analysis of the specific situation in their country, from the point of view of the ATMO-ACCESS participants and RI operators. The second questionnaire comprised a collection of questions to be addressed to national stakeholders and funding agencies to get feedback on their opinions and strategies.

Questionnaire for NAPCs

The questionnaire for NAPCs, provided in [Annex 1: Questionnaire for National Access Contact Persons](#), aims at analyzing the funding modalities of RIs in the different countries in general. The questions concern the national roadmap process (if applicable) and the stakeholders responsible for funding the implementation and operation of RIs. Furthermore, modalities and funding opportunities for access to national and European RIs are enquired. The NAPCs were asked to evaluate their national situation regarding a strategy for sustainable access to RIs, including co-funding opportunities.

Questionnaire for National Funding Agencies and Stakeholders

The material in [Annex 3: Questionnaire for National Funding Agencies and Stakeholders](#) was prepared to support NAPCs in their task to contact national funding agencies and stakeholders. This second questionnaire was thought as a proposal, which could be adjusted by the NAPCs to their national needs. In the investigations, particular interest was placed on embedding access to RIs directly into national funding agency programs or researcher funding applications,

thus avoiding a mismatch between requirements and access capacity. Next to the questionnaire with a proposed list of questions that could be addressed to the stakeholders, additional text material was provided, which 1) briefly introduces the ATMO-ACCESS project and the aim of the questionnaire and 2) gives an extended description of the H2020 pilot programme dedicated to new and sustainable access modalities for distributed European RIs, as well as the three selected RIs that are working in this programme.

4 Results and Analysis

Answers from NAPCs

The questionnaire for NAPCs has been answered by 14 country representatives. Table 1 briefly summarizes the outcome regarding existing access modalities and co-funding options. The complete list of answers to all questions is provided in [Annex 2: Answers from National Access Contact Persons](#).

Table 1: Overview of existing access modalities and co-funding options as seen by the NAPCs

Country	Potential options for advanced access modalities
AT: Austria	There is no (co-)funding of transnational access and no interest of the agency to develop any strategy.
BG: Bulgaria	There is no (co-)funding of transnational access. However, BG considers membership contributions to ERICs as a kind of access support to the RIs. Solutions for future co-funding mechanisms are discussed at ministerial level.
CZ: Czech Republic	There is no funding of access, and no strategy exists so far. A new roadmap will be published which may contain such opportunities.
DE: Germany	Solutions for funding of national and limited international access exist through research projects. Co-funding is realized only via in-kind contributions of the Research Performing Organisations (RPO).
DK: Denmark	There is no (co-)funding of transnational access, but access can be supported through specific research projects. No strategic developments are known.
ES: Spain	Access can be funded as part of national or regional research projects, but also fees are applied. A co-funding strategy is not known.
FI: Finland	There is a positive attitude of the funding agency regarding co-funding of access in EU programmes.
FR: France	Traditionally, bi-lateral agreements are preferred by the funding agency. Co-funding is realized only via in-kind contributions of the RPOs.
IT: Italy	Support of access provision is part of the national programme for implementation and operation of RIs. The country is open to align its national programme with the European innovation programmes.

NO: Norway	Operational costs for the use of any research infrastructure are eligible costs in all funding schemes of the Research Council, but there is no strategy for co-funding of transnational access.
PL: Poland	Access is funded at project basis and many opportunities exist, but there is no clear strategy for co-funding of transnational access.
RO: Romania	There is no funding of access. Access to RIs is a poorly known concept in the country and in general realized by in-kind contributions of the RPOs.
SE: Sweden	Access is to be provided by the RPOs, when projects are supported by the Swedish Research Council. In general, a co-funding rate of 50% applies for the RPOs.
UK: United Kingdom	Access opportunities are diverse and individual, no specific co-funding options are known.

Answers from National Funding Agencies and Stakeholders

Feedback from national stakeholders and funding agencies could be gathered in six countries. Table 2 briefly summarizes the answers regarding potential options for advanced access modalities and co-funding options. The complete list of answers to all questions is provided in [Annex 4: Answers from National Funding Agencies and Stakeholders](#).

Table 2: Summary of feedback from national stakeholders and funding agencies regarding potential options for advanced access modalities

Country	Potential options for advanced access modalities
BG: Bulgaria	The Bulgarian Ministry of Education and Science is open to discuss co-funding options depending on scope, goals, expected results and impact and the benefits for the Bulgarian researchers and research organisations. Access funding would be limited to national users and support of projects under bilateral agreements.
ES: Spain	The Spanish “Agencia Estatal de Investigación” does not consider supporting TNA via co-funding schemes.
FI: Finland	The Research Council of Finland finds it worth discussing new access modalities and co-funding schemes, but has no options defined yet.
NO: Norway	The Research Council of Norway does not consider supporting TNA via co-funding schemes.
RO: Romania	The Romanian Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization is open to consider TNA provision, e.g. in Joint Programming Initiatives, but sees many difficulties in setting up the rules, managing the process, and evaluating the results etc. Co-funding schemes would be limited to national users.
UK: United Kingdom	The Natural Environment Research Council does not consider new access modalities beyond the already existing support of RIs for access provision. Any access funding would be limited to UK-based researchers and eligible RPOs.

Analysis of the Current Situation in Europe

The situation in Europe is clearly very heterogeneous. While most countries have funding opportunities for national access to RIs, they do not have a strategy for funding or co-funding transnational access to their national facilities. Most funding agencies traditionally support national or bilateral research projects, and access to RIs can be part of such projects, i.e. access-related costs are eligible expenses. As R&D projects are funded through competitive calls for proposals, the actual amount of money spent on access is usually not pre-determined or accounted for and is often simply 'hidden' in the funding lines. As a result, pre-defined co-funding schemes do not fit in with established concepts of research funding in many countries.

In addition, national laws often restrict the use of funds to the support of national researchers and do not allow funding of TNA. Another obstacle for stakeholders is the bureaucracy and the potential lack of transparency that could be associated with the new access modalities. On the one hand, funding agencies demand that all actors, i.e. funders and access providers, must be involved in the decision-making process. On the other hand, several stakeholders state that they do not have the capacity to deal with such new modalities and do not want to be involved in the day-to-day decisions (e.g. the selection of access projects). They would prefer to leave this mandate to the RPOs who provide access to their RIs. Finally, it appears that the implementation of new access modalities and co-financing options would often be left to the RPOs, which would be heavily burdened, with the risk of reducing their access capacity.

An exception is Italy, where a national programme for access to environmental RIs has recently been set up. The approach is briefly presented in the next section and serves as a first example of the implementation of new access modalities and co-financing options at the national level that could be used as a guideline for other countries.

The Italian National Access Support Programme within ITINERIS

ITINERIS, the Italian Integrated Environmental Research Infrastructures System¹, is dedicated to building the Italian Hub of Research Infrastructures in the environmental scientific domain (<https://itineris.cnr.it>). It shall support the observation and study of environmental processes in the atmosphere, marine domain, terrestrial biosphere, and geosphere, providing access to data and services and supporting the Country in addressing current and expected environmental challenges. A significant portion of the activities in the project is meant to promote, facilitate and support harmonised access to services and resources of the participating RIs. In this

¹ IR0000032 – ITINERIS, Italian Integrated Environmental Research Infrastructures System (D.D. n. 130/2022 - CUP B53C22002150006) Funded by EU - Next Generation EU PNRR- Mission 4 "Education and Research" - Component 2: "From research to business" - Investment 3.1: "Fund for the realisation of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructures"

framework, the coordinator (CNR, National Research Council) has decided to use part of the budget dedicated to financing access within the ITINERIS project, to experiment, in collaboration with ACTRIS, an access programme supported by national funds. The ACTRIS – ITINERIS test program will design, implement and test specific access processes, with operations and workflows tailored to fit national funding requirements, and aimed at ensuring RIs' facilities' seamless utilization. The criteria will include either the access of EU facilities by Italian users, or the access to Italian facilities by users from foreign institutions.

The ACTRIS – ITINERIS pilot will be managed by the Service and Access Management Unit (SAMU) of the ACTRIS Head Office, which is hosted by the CNR in Italy. The possibility of using Italian funding is a unique opportunity to test national-co-funded access, which, along with EU-funded access and access possibly financed by other sources, could become a component of the sustainability of RIs' access programmes currently studied in the frame of various ongoing projects.

5 Summary and Conclusions

This document has been prepared to describe the efforts of ATMO-ACCESS to liaise with national stakeholders and funding agencies and collect information on the situation in the different countries regarding the (co-)funding of access to distributed European RIs. Two questionnaires were developed. The first one was dedicated to the NAPCs and aimed at collecting information from the point of view of the access providers (NAPCs as representatives of the RPOs).

The second questionnaire was prepared to support the NAPCs in contacting their national stakeholders and funding agencies. The material was thought as a guideline, which could be adapted to the national needs, and contained also general information on ATMO-ACCESS and the European pilot activity dedicated to new and sustainable access modalities for distributed European RIs.

While many NAPCs actively participated in the discussion, answered the questionnaire, and described the situation in their countries in detail, it proved to be a challenge to get feedback from the national funding agencies, especially in the form of written responses to the questionnaire. The reasons for this clearly lie in the lack of national concepts for funding access to distributed RIs and the skepticism towards the creation of new funding lines. Although many countries support access to RIs more or less indirectly through their national R&D programmes, structural obstacles prevent the establishment of well-defined national access programmes. The example of Italy shows that such obstacles can be overcome through targeted initiatives. Stakeholders should intensify the discussion on the needs for sustainable access to distributed RIs, and countries should work on ways to implement national access programmes.

Annex 1: Questionnaire for National Access Contact Persons (NAPCs)

1) Questions on national funding mechanisms for the implementation and operation of research infrastructures

- a) Does your country have a National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures? If yes, are distributed atmospheric research infrastructures (national parts of ACTRIS, IAGOS, ICOS) part of the National Roadmap?
- b) How is the implementation and operation of distributed atmospheric research infrastructures funded in your country? If applicable, how is this related to the National Roadmap process?
- c) Are there different funding mechanisms existing for other types of research infrastructure?
- d) Is there other information on your national funding strategy that you consider important in this context?

2) Questions on national funding strategies for access to research infrastructures

- a) If applicable, is funding of national and/or transnational access to research infrastructures part of your National Roadmap process?
- b) How is national and/or international access to research infrastructures funded in your country in general? Which funding agencies provide support for access to research infrastructures and in which framework is funding provided? Does this include also access to distributed atmospheric research infrastructures?
- c) Does your country already have a strategy for co-funding of transnational access to research infrastructures?
- d) Is there other information on your national funding strategy that you consider important, e.g., in view of co-funding opportunities?

3) Questions on possible future access modalities and opportunities

- a) Are there ongoing efforts in your country to develop a national strategy for sustainable access modalities and co-funding opportunities?

- b) How do you, as NCP, see your national situation regarding access modalities and co-funding opportunities?

Annex 2: Answers from National Access Contact Persons (NAPCs)

1) Questions on national funding mechanisms for the implementation and operation of research infrastructures

- a) Does your country have a National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures? If yes, are distributed atmospheric research infrastructures (national parts of ACTRIS, IAGOS, ICOS) part of the National Roadmap?

AT: The BMBWF (Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research) in Austria is responsible for setting the strategic direction of research and education in the country, including the development of research infrastructures. However, right now no official roadmap exists, but there is an action plan: <https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/Themen/Forschung/Forschung-in-%C3%96sterreich/Forschungsinfrastruktur.html>

BG: Yes, Bulgaria has a National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures (NRRI) for the time period 2020-2027. The roadmap can be found here: <https://web.mon.bg/en/100994>

The atmospheric research infrastructures of Bulgaria are part of the National Roadmap and ACTRIS-BG (<http://actris-bg.eu/en/actris-bulgaria/>) part of it and is in the ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) Roadmap since 2016.

CZ: Yes, Czech Republic has National Roadmap for RI. (<https://www.vyzkumne-infrastruktury.cz/en/roadmap-of-large-research-infrastructures-of-the-czech-republic/>). The latest edition of the Roadmap, updated in 2019, introduces the strategy of large research infrastructures funding in 2016-2022. ACTRIS and ICOS are part of the National Roadmap.

DE: Germany does have a National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures, and ACTRIS-D, IAGOS-D, and ICOS-D are part of it.

DK: Yes, Villum is both an ACTRIS, ICOS station.

ES: Spain does not have a National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures as such.

FI: Yes, Finland has a National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures for the time period 2021-2024. In Finland, the umbrella RI is the INAR RI (Integrated Atmospheric and Earth System Research Infrastructure), which coordinates the Finnish national contributions to four ESFRIs (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures): ICOS (Integrated Carbon Observation

System), ACTRIS (Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure), eLTER (Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, Critical Zone & Socio-Ecological Research Infrastructure) and AnaEE (Infrastructure for Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems).

FR: France does have a National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures, and ACTRIS-FR, IAGOS-FR, and ICOS-FR are part of it.

IT: Yes, Italy has a National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures named “Piano Nazionale Infrastrutture di Ricerca (PNIR) 2021 – 2027” published at 20/10/2021 by the National Ministry of University and Research [[Decreto Ministeriale n.1082 del 10-09-2021 - PNIR 2021 - 2027.pdf \(mur.gov.it\)](#)]. ACTRIS and ICOS are distributed atmospheric research infrastructures part of the National Roadmap.

NO: Yes.

<https://www.forskningsradet.no/sok-om-finansiering/midler-fra-forskningsradet/infrastruktur/norsk-veikart/>

PL: Yes, Poland has National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures, ACTRIS and ICOS are on the map.

RO: Romania has a National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures. ACTRIS-RO and ICOS-RO are on the national roadmap.

SE: Yes, Sweden has a National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures (<https://www.vr.se/english/analysis/reports/our-reports/2022-11-25-results-of-needs-inventory-2021-2022.html>) that is updated every second year. ICOS and ACTRIS are on the highest category in this roadmap and are currently also funded by the Swedish Research Council.

UK: Yes, there is a roadmap, but it is high level, and although distributed networks are included as the kind of infrastructure needed, the roadmap is primarily concerned with investment at a much larger scale than the UK nodes of ACTRIS, IAGOS and ICOS. Colleagues are currently however considering a bid to the funding councils for support of the ESFRI networks, in line with the Roadmap.

b) How is the implementation and operation of distributed atmospheric research infrastructures funded in your country? If applicable, how is this related to the National Roadmap process?

AT: Funding for the implementation and operation of RI's directly comes from the BMBWF (Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research). Funding of the physical infrastructure mainly comes from the RPOs. However, the RPOs are also funded by BMBWF. RIs are

mentioned in the contract - called "Leistungsvereinbarung" between RPOs and BMBWF. Additional funding for instruments comes from FWF (Austrian Science Fund). There is a biennial call.

BG: The implementation and operations of ACTRIS-BG, including costs for operating the nodes of the Observational sites in Bulgaria, has been funded by the Ministry of education and science (MES).

CZ: For the most part, atmospheric research infrastructures are funded by the Ministry of Education Youth and Sports. Another source of funding is provided by the Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic.

DE: The implementation of distributed atmospheric research infrastructures has been funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) as part of the National Roadmap process. In-kind contributions of the RPOs are required in addition. Long-term operation of the National Facilities has to be guaranteed by the RPOs, i.e., all operational costs have to be covered at institutional level. Central European Facilities are supported by different ministries, in particular the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (BMUV) and the Federal Ministry for Digital and Transport (BMDV). Since implementation and operation are funded by different stakeholders, agreements between them need to be in place before any support is given.

DK: We have grants for building up the infrastructures but miss funding for long term monitoring.

ES: In the case of ACTRIS, the membership fee is paid entirely by the Ministry of Science and Innovation (but this is not necessarily the general case). The operation costs are supported by the RPOs, which pay salaries and housing, and by funding from competitive International, National, and Regional projects. In the case of Central Facility units, this funding scheme applies only to 70% of their operation costs, the rest coming from ACTRIS ERIC.

FI: The national contribution to the RI operation for the distributed RIs is funded through a combination of RPO direct funding and competitive funding applied from the Research Council of Finland (formerly Academy of Finland). The latter supports mainly development of the RIs and the former supports operative work. The Research Council of Finland operates the Research Infrastructure Committee (FIRI), which makes decisions regarding the RI funding.

FR: The implementation and operations of ACTRIS-FR, including costs for operating the nodes of the Central Facilities in France, has been funded by different sources of funding but mainly by CNRS as part of the Earth observation strategy (Services Nationaux d'Observation) and by the Ministry for Research (MESR) as part of specific investment programs managed both locally (LaBEX) and nationally (EquipEX). In addition, In-kind contributions of the RPOs (including

universities) are providing a strong work-force amounting to approx. 60 FTE. An agreement binding ACTRIS-FR stakeholders was signed in 2020 and all costs are monitored through a full-cost rolling document.

IT: The implementation of research infrastructures (distributed atmospheric RI or others) is funded through a recurrent competitive call for proposals one for each national programming period. The last one was in the framework of National Operational Programming Period 2014-2020 ("Programma Operativo Nazionale Ricerca e Innovazione 2014-2020" (PON R&I)) aimed to the implementation and strengthening of national research infrastructures. A specific requirement for the eligibility to the call for proposals is that the IR has to be part of PNIR.

Currently, a call for proposal for funding RIs is open in the framework of PNNR –Recovery and Resilience Plan, with a very huge investment.

The operation of research infrastructures is supported through an annual national contribution (FOE) of the ministry and, more important, the RPOs' in-kind support.

NO: Implementation and operation is funded for the first 5 years. No link to the national roadmap and all applications are evaluated through international expert panels together with an evaluation of the strategic importance and relevance to research priorities according to the long-term plan for research by the government.

PL: Application for National Roadmap requires, among others, provisions of the investment plan and operational costs in the future together with proposed sources of funding. There are a number of possible sources based on competition. The use of structure funds for R&D is favorable during implementation, however, there is also a dedicated investment program of the Ministry of Science. Operational costs of infrastructures are covered in general by the so-called SPUB program that is applicable for special scientific equipment, through single labs to e.g. polar stations.

Moreover, after signing ERIC, national consortium may apply for a special program supporting participation in ERIC that covers: ERIC fee, investments needed (that are not covered by structure funds and ministry's investment program) and operational costs not included in the SPUB program.

RO: In the case of ERIC infrastructures, the membership fee is paid entirely by the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization (currently the case for ACTRIS but not for ICOS because Romania is not yet a member). The operation costs are supported partially by the RPOs as in-kind (working time of personnel) and partially through national programs which cover the base for research activities (different for research institutes and for the universities; the activities can be embedded in the general framework proposed by the research institutions in their 4-years plan). Competitive calls dedicated to research infrastructures are also launched about each 2

years, however these are very specific and generally supporting the capacity building. In the case of Central Facility unit (CARS-AHL-INOE), this funding scheme applies only to 70% of their operation costs, the rest coming from ACTRIS ERIC.

SE: The process is handled by the Swedish Research Council. There is now a new round of prioritization ongoing (deadline 7 Nov) even for those already funded, such as ACTRIS Sweden (funding 2022-2026). We will submit our renewed request for prioritization on 3 Nov. The partner RPOs need to fund at least 50% of the RI budget. Therefore, there is also a parallel process involving all Swedish universities to prioritize all requests for RI support on the national level.

Note that the membership fee for Sweden in ACTRIS ERIC has to come through the Swedish Research Council, and we therefore need to have ACTRIS acknowledged and funded as a Swedish national RI.

UK: They are primarily funded through the NERC Centres (NCAS, CEH, NOC, BGS, BAS, PML) which are charged by NERC with carrying out long-term research. Some infrastructure nodes are also supported by Universities, and there are plans for direct Government support to some ACTRIS nodes in the future.

c) Are there different funding mechanisms existing for other types of research infrastructure?

AT: -

BG: There is a variety of research infrastructure types – e-infrastructures, one physical site, networks of laboratories (for example) and data centers, etc. Depending on the form and legal status and whether a research infrastructure is a consortium of organizations or is a facility managed by a research institute (for example) – there are different funding options, whereas each of these options has relevant eligibility criteria.

Research infrastructures can apply for project funding under relevant national and international programs and initiatives. Bulgarian research infrastructures included in the updated NRRI represent projects and facilities that are validated as important on national and in a number of cases – on international level. However not all of these research infrastructures receive annual public funding via NRRI as a funding instrument.

Based on a number of criteria and following a complex procedure, annual funding is allocated to NRRI facilities and projects (infrastructures). The Ministry of Education and Science is the financial coordinator for the NRRI.

CZ: No, there are no funding mechanisms other than the ministries mentioned earlier.

DE: The German Science Foundation (DFG) supports the implementation of and the access to specific national research infrastructures such as research aircraft and vessels, partly together with BMBF and national research organizations such as the Helmholtz Association. DFG also supports research infrastructure at universities, e.g.:

https://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/programmes/infrastructure/index.html

https://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/funding_opportunities/research_vessel/index.html).

DK: We must apply in free competition with other research projects.

ES: Yes. In some cases, a contribution to the membership fee is requested from the participating RPOs.

FI: There are separate calls for RIs that are indicated in the national roadmap and arising new RIs. The FIRI also oversees the updates for the national RI roadmap.

FR: The national funding agency Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR) does not directly support the implementation of and the access to specific national research infrastructures such as research aircraft and vessels, or atmospheric facilities, besides through a specific EquipEX program (e.g., OBS4CLIM: <https://www.obs4clim.fr/> involving ACTRIS-FR, ICOS-FR, IAGOS-FR). However, ANR is regularly funding projects using atmospheric research facilities that are part of the national research facilities, but this is within collaborative research projects where the group holding the facility is a partner in the project. In no way this shall be considered neither as implementation support, nor operation support, nor support for long-term operations.

IT: The funding mechanisms of research infrastructure part of PNIR are described in b).

NO: Operational costs for the use of research infrastructures are eligible costs in all funding schemes in the Research Council.

PL: According to my knowledge NO. That means all RIs are treated equally.

RO: Yes. In some cases considered of strategic importance (e.g. Danubius, ELI) the Ministry provides direct and dedicated funding.

SE: Not really for RIs at the national level. It is supposed to come through the Swedish Research Council. Some Swedish universities have RI funds, but these are handled very differently from one university to the other. ACTRIS Sweden (and ICOS Sweden) has received RI funding support from Lund University and the Faculties involved. The competition is tough.

ACTRIS-related observations at Hyltemossa and Norunda are also partly supported by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency motivated by air quality.

Private donations are also possible. There are private foundations (*stiftelser*) that can fund also fairly extensive RIs. We will examine if we can get some support like that for our co-located ACTRIS-ICOS stations.

UK: For major infrastructure such as ships and Antarctic bases, direct bids to Government are made for the initial capital, but the running costs are met by NERC primarily.

d) Is there other information on your national funding strategy that you consider important in this context?

AT: -

BG: The frame that sets the goals, priorities, stages and steps, expected results and deliverables as well as relevant time periods is formulated in the National Strategy for Development of Scientific Research in the Republic of Bulgaria 2017-2030. National funding and funding under various international programs and initiatives (including FP Horizon Europe) are considered.

CZ: The future update of the Roadmap is scheduled for 2023, when the new multiannual financial framework 2023-2029 for the support of large research infrastructures from public funds of the Czech Republic will be launched.

DE: The National Roadmap has not been updated regularly. It is unclear how the National Roadmap process will be continued and if existing National Roadmap projects will be supported also in the future.

DK: We apply for funding at Danish public and private funds as well as for support from EU funds e.g., Horizon etc.

ES: -

FI: The Research Council of Finland has special targeted calls for the headquarters of ACTRIS and ICOS to support the operation and development of the headquarters activities. A specific detail related to ACTRIS is that the funding for ACTRIS Head Office is split in half between the Ministry of Education and Culture and Ministry of Transport and Communications. The former funding is managed through The Research Council of Finland and FIRI whereas the latter funding is managed by the ministry in question. Typically, the funding distribution is 50/50 between the two ministries.

FR: The National Roadmap is updated regularly. Next update is 2024. No real risk of seeing ACTRIS-FR, ICOS-FR or IAGOS-FR out of the roadmap but perhaps incentives to Atmospheric Research RIs to coordinate their operations.

IT: The PNIR provides strategic orientation for policies related to the crucial topic of Research Infrastructures and aims to provide greater detail on a technical-strategic level, defining and updating national priorities.

The PNIR identifies the priority research infrastructures for Italy by adopting, for this purpose, European methods and criteria, and provides the possibility of systematizing what is already present in our Country.

NO: Long-term operation of the National Facilities at Birkenes and Zeppelin is funded through the Norwegian Environment Agency and by NILU, whereas the activity at Trollhaugen is funded by the Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment. Also, important support for the ACTRIS Data Centre is provided by the European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme (EMEP) through long-term contracts.

PL: No.

RO: -

SE: As explained above: (i) Ensure that ACTRIS is on the Swedish Roadmap; (ii) Secure continued RPO support; (iii) Secure funding from the Swedish Research Council (typically every 5th year); (iv) Further develop our collaboration with ICOS Sweden, also examining the possibility for merging to form a combined ICOS-ACTRIS national RI in the future.

UK: We are moving slowly to a more strategic investment strategy, but the political turbulence of the past few years had made this difficult.

2) Questions on national funding strategies for access to research infrastructures

a) If applicable, is funding of national and/or transnational access to research infrastructures part of your National Roadmap process?

AT: -

BG: Funding of national and/or transnational access to research infrastructures is not part of the National Roadmap process, meaning there is no dedicated financial resources available to cover or compensate for the access to RIs and there is no applicable option to cover any relevant costs for the users (i.e. provide free access). Since access falls under operation, RPOs are considered to be responsible for access provision.

CZ: Current National Roadmap doesn't mention NA (National Access) / TNA.

DE: Funding of national and/or transnational access to research infrastructures is not part of the National Roadmap process. Since access falls under operation, RPOs are considered to be responsible for access provision.

DK: No.

ES: There is no National Roadmap in Spain. However there exists a map of Unique Science and Technology Infrastructures (ICTS) with a variety of access modalities that are discussed in the next paragraph.

FI: No particular access program is established. However, open access and collaboration have been identified key development areas for the RIs in the National RI roadmap 2021-2024. The amount of access (as the number of users) is one of the Key Performance Indicators for the RIs. Scientific projects funded by Research Council of Finland are recommended to include international mobility. This provides indirect support for access to observation sites and facilities outside of Finland by providing travel, lodging and other costs that arise during the mobility.

FR: Funding of national and/or transnational access to research infrastructures is not part of the National Roadmap process. Access is somehow funded through collaborative projects of ANR. E.g. in the case of ACTRIS-FR, most of the research facilities are recognized as “facilities of national interest” and as such receive some limited funding which, in principle, can be considered to provide access, but this is really limited funds.

IT: Access to RIs is a strategic pillar of the PNIR, but no specific funding was foreseen.

In the PNNR call for proposals for strengthening RIs, it is foreseen to fund TNA as long as to meet the eligibility conditions of PNNR funds.

NO: No, but Operational costs for the use of research infrastructures are eligible costs in all funding schemes in the Research Council.

PL: Costs of access to RI may be included in application for National Roadmap, however it is not mandatory. Mandatory is information on how and for what parties (academia, business, etc.) the access will be provided.

RO: No. Access to infrastructure is a poorly known concept in Romania (except access to data).

SE: In principle, our contract with Swedish Research Council requires us to offer national access to researchers free of charge. This is of course limited to our capabilities for offering this support. We do not support travel and shipping but can offer accommodation on-site. The same is basically also true for access for transnational researchers. Commercial users pay full costs.

UK: The Roadmap is primarily concerned with investment in the UK. Facilities like CERN and ESA are supported through international treaties.

- b) How is national and/or international access to research infrastructures funded in your country in general? Which funding agencies provide support for access to research infrastructures and in which framework is funding provided? Does this include also access to distributed atmospheric research infrastructures?

AT: -

BG: There is no specific funding source for access to distributed atmospheric research infrastructures, but access costs can be claimed in research proposals.

CZ: All NA / TNA are paid by the organization or RIs.

DE: There exist programs for access to specific national research infrastructures such as research aircraft and vessels. Funding is provided by DFG in collaboration with BMBF and the organizations that operate the facilities (mainly members of the Helmholtz Association, partly also members of the Max Planck Society and the Leibniz Association). Funding is mainly provided for researchers from national research institutions, international access is limited, e.g.: <https://portal-forschungsschiffe.de/en/index.html>

There is no specific funding source for access to distributed atmospheric research infrastructures, but access costs can be claimed in research proposals, e.g., for DFG projects.

DK: They are funded through support to specific projects that then has to pay for travel and stay.

ES: It is difficult to respond in a general way. Depending on the infrastructure, funding may come from a mix of national and regional funding. In some cases, an access fee is requested from the user. The fee amount can in turn depend on whether the access is “on demand” or competitive. Others do not request a fee, but the travel and subsistence costs are paid by the user. Some may offer travel and subsistence, within the limits of available budget, to users of Spanish research institutions.

FI: There is no specific funding for national or transnational access. However, there are mobility programmes, typically with targeted countries via bi-lateral agreements. These mobility programmes can support access to the RIs as well as support associated scientific work. In normal Research Council of Finland research grants, mobility is not a direct requirement, but supported strongly as it connects the scientific work in Finland closely with the international scientific communities.

Overall, Access is not directly supported but facilitated through mobility funded through

research projects. It does not matter, if the RI is distributed or not. This support can be used for Finnish scientists accessing RI outside of Finland or foreign researchers accessing Finnish RIs. Typically, the support cannot be used for RI costs, but costs arising from travel, lodging, and shipping costs. Some of the access costs can be supported through purchased services in the case that there is a matching invoice for the cost.

FR: There exist programs for access to specific national research infrastructures such as research aircraft and vessels. Funding is provided by ANR and the organizations that operate the facilities (CNRS, IFREMER, Météo-France). Funding is mainly provided for researchers from national research institutions, international access is limited. There is no specific funding source for access to distributed atmospheric research infrastructures. Access costs are not formally recognized by ANR but as mentioned, support can be claimed in research grants, e.g., for ANR projects.

IT: The Italian Ministry of University and Research is the funding agency providing support for access to research infrastructures in the framework of PNNR mentioned above.

NO: Operational costs for the use of any research infrastructure are eligible costs in all funding schemes in the Research Council.

PL: There is no segregation regarding to type of infrastructure. If access to RI is not included in the aforementioned “support of ERIC” then access is funded through individual research projects. For example, National Science Center (NCN) has opened call for: “research projects implemented by Polish research teams with the use of large international research equipment”. However, NCN has answered “The National Science Center does not finance open access to infrastructure” when inquired in questionnaire for financing agencies. There is also special path in Ministry of Science for co-financed international project that is applicable for co-financed access to RI.

RO: Access to infrastructure is funded by the RPOs as in-kind and/or through EC projects when applicable. For national users (e.g. scientists, PhD and Master students) generally a protocol is signed between institutions for collaborative work.

SE: Access is mainly funded by the Swedish Research Council as part of a national RI, where the partner RPOs co-fund at least 50%. RPOs may of course also choose to support access in a separate process, but that is hard to get for those RIs who are not a national RI. At the Engineering Faculty LTH at Lund University, there is an initiative called “LTH Open Door” offering access to some of our larger LTH RIs, including the Aerosol Laboratory (<https://www.lth.se/english/opendoor/>). We will most likely get our Hyltemossa ACTRIS station on that list soon(ish). LTH recently classified ACTRIS Hyltemossa as an RI of strategic importance.

UK: The general picture is complex, with different approaches taken by different research councils. For the Environment area, NERC supports national-scale infrastructures of two kinds: Major infrastructure (e.g. ships, FAAM aircraft and Antarctic bases) and National Facilities (E.g. the Atmospheric Measurement and Observation Facility, AMOF). Academic researchers can apply through different funding streams for access to these Facilities, which is peer-reviewed. FAAM (www.faam.ac.uk) and AMOF (www.amof.ac.uk) are the two facilities most relevant to atmospheric research, but NERC does support around 10-12 different National Facilities (<https://www.ukri.org/councils/nerc/facilities-and-resources/>). Long-term measurements are not considered as Facilities in the UK – these are seen as long-term research activities, which, in NERC's case, are the province of its Centres.

c) Does your country already have a strategy for co-funding of transnational access to research infrastructures?

AT: -

BG: Bulgaria is a member of 11 existing ERICs and is committed (will be a founding member) to participate in LOFAR ERIC. Participation in ERICs incurs annual contribution fee per country that covers not only administration but also access, training, etc. Bulgaria is a CERN (and DUBNA) member state. This aspect is covered by the National Strategy for Development of Scientific Research in the Republic of Bulgaria 2017-2030. Bulgaria has and implements a National plan for the development of Open Science Initiatives (Open Science Strategy).

CZ: There is no strategy for co-funding of transnational access to research infrastructures.

DE: A strategy for co-funding of transnational access to research infrastructures does not exist.

DK: No.

ES: I don't know.

FI: No.

FR: A strategy for co-funding of transnational access to research infrastructures does not exist.

IT: The PNIR provides strategic orientation: about the access, it is encouraged the alignment with European innovation programmes, in particular Horizon Europe.

About the sustainability of access, both from a financial point of view – for researchers and potential users, and for the infrastructures themselves, “it can be promoted with the contribution of different sources and co-financing mechanisms that involve the national, regional, European, private funds, etc. to cover the costs incurred by infrastructures for providing access.”

NO: No.

PL: According to my knowledge NO.

RO: No.

SE: Not that I know of. Except through the national RIs as explained above. There are notable exceptions, for instance the Swedish synchrotron Max IV (which is part of Lund University) and the neutron source ESS (an ERIC), also located in Lund. Transnational access to Max IV is free of charge for all researchers, and the same will be the case for ESS once it is up and running. This is the international standard for all X-ray and neutron sources worldwide. CERN is another example, where Sweden and other countries put in a lot of in-kind contributions and gain access. Similar principles of transnational access could perhaps be agreed between the ACTRIS ERIC countries and/or the EU. This would benefit all countries and strengthen the ERA.

I can discuss possible options for TNA in ACTRIS ERIC with Sara Moa, our ACTRIS Sweden contact person at the Swedish Research Council, and the Swedish representative in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly.

UK: No.

d) Is there other information on your national funding strategy that you consider important, e.g., in view of co-funding opportunities?

AT: -

BG: Since the National Roadmap process requires an institutional commitment for the operation of National Facilities on the long term, national co-funding of transnational access might be seen as the responsibility of the RPOs. However, as mentioned above, funding of national access via research projects is in principle possible.

CZ: -

DE: Since the National Roadmap process requires an institutional commitment for the operation of National Facilities on the long term, national co-funding of transnational access might be seen as the responsibility of the RPOs. However, as mentioned above, funding of national access via research projects is in principle possible.

DK: I wish there was.

ES: I don't have such information.

FI: Informally the Research Council of Finland has reacted positively towards co-funding access to RIs in EU work programme.

FR: Since the National Roadmap process requires an institutional commitment for the operation of National Facilities on the long term, national co-funding of transnational access might be seen as the responsibility of the RPOs. However, as mentioned above, funding of national access via research projects is in principle possible.

IT: The PNIR is a comprehensive strategic document and also co-funding opportunities are encouraged.

NO: -.

PL: No.

RO: Romania has annual budgets, therefore funding is generally planned and provided on short-term projects (variety of types, variety of funding sources, generally competitive). The only constant commitment is at the side of the RPOs. I doubt this will change in the near future.

SE: RPO co-funding is essential in the Swedish system, as well as possible funding from private foundations, then mostly for equipment.

UK: From time to time there have been co-funded research initiatives with other countries, based on the large facilities. This is particularly common with research ships, where barter arrangements bring huge savings in fuel, but there have been few such initiatives in the atmospheric area.

3) Questions on possible future access modalities and opportunities

- a) Are there ongoing efforts in your country to develop a national strategy for sustainable access modalities and co-funding opportunities?

AT: -

BG: There are relevant solutions discussed at ministerial level in Bulgaria. Since such options cannot be a standalone per-case solutions, discussions mean to determine the format and functionality of such sustainable access modalities so that they adhere to and bring results under all applicable strategies (development of research, I3S, economic development, innovation and growth, triple helix).

CZ: During this year the new National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures will be released. There is a possibility that it will contain a plan for developing a national strategy for sustainable access modalities and co-funding.

DE: Discussions on sustainable access modalities have been started at BMBF in 2022, but nothing is known about a strategy development.

DK: No, not to my knowledge.

ES: I don't know. This question belongs in my opinion in the questionnaire for the funding agency.

FI: No.

FR: The issue of access to distributed RI facilities and the expectations of the EU commission regarding the sharing of transnational access costs for accessing atmospheric research facilities was discussed with ANR. In EU projects, access costs are validated by the relevant administrative services (regional CNRS services) as a basis for reimbursement. These costs are not recognized by ANR in collaborative projects as the processes follow different procedures. ANR has an independent project review which can independently accept or not the access costs.

IT: -

NO: No.

PL: Even if it is, it is not made visible and communicated to public.

RO: No.

SE: Again, not that I know of. I will bring it up with the Swedish Research Council.

UK: No.

b) How do you, as NCP, see your national situation regarding access modalities and co-funding opportunities?

AT: National TNA funding from the FWF (Austrian science fund) is not possible. After a personal meeting with the responsible person, it is clear that this funding agency is not willing to take the bureaucratic burden for small TNA projects with a volume of less than 10 k€. Therefore, no co funding from FWF. Also, the ministry feels not in charge of supporting such projects.

BG: On my opinion there is a good working relation between the ACTRIS-BG and the Ministry of education and science regarding the RI support as well.

CZ: The funding of European-level Research Infrastructures and National Facilities embedded in the European RIs are very unpredictable. Also, there are some indications that some of the large research infrastructures may be excluded from a National Roadmap or at least the authorities are trying to find a way how to do that. There is currently no national plan for co-funding of transnational access.

DE: In Germany, the support for European Research Infrastructures is very restrictive. The involvement of several stakeholders, often without clear responsibilities, leads to lengthy and cumbersome discussion and decision processes. So far, a strategy for sustainable access modalities is missing, and there is no national plan for co-funding of transnational access.

DK: It is difficult. Private funds and EU funds are the most promising.

ES: Given the variety of access modalities to other research infrastructures, it is possible that opportunities can be found, although it will not be easy.

FI: There is a good working relation between the ACTRIS-FI and the Research Council of Finland regarding the RI support as well as active collaboration between ACTRIS-FI and the two ministries supporting the RI development.

FR: As mentioned, the use of distributed RI facilities is very common in "traditional" ANR projects, generally implemented through scientific collaboration, with the facility operator being a consortium partner. There is an ongoing shift towards a more generic use of facility access (via service-based billing), supported by the authorities overseeing these facilities. This shift requires widespread recognition of access costs. Membership in an RI (which establishes its full costs) could provide the appropriate context both at the national and European levels. It is possible in an ANR project that French partners would require the use of a facility located outside of France and reimbursements of access would take place through appropriate billing of the third parties. As for national project, ANR can independently consider reviewing the access costs. Clearly, a simplification would be eligibility of EU costs and their certification conditions with national funding agencies. Like other European Commission calls in Horizon Europe, projects funding transnational access to RI facilities (Pillar 1 Research Infrastructures) could evolve towards a more systematic use of the CO-FUND mechanism. No mechanisms exist in France to organize CO-FUND, besides through in-kind contributions (from CNRS researchers and/or university staff). ANR is more used to bilateral agreements with other funding agencies in Europe and beyond which can provide a mutually beneficial approach for evolution towards bilateral calls. But this has never been used as a tool for funding access specifically but for joint research projects only. Being a funding agency, ANR is not part of the French stakeholders in ACTRIS ERIC. ACTRIS ERIC cannot be a partner in ANR projects (to be confirmed) so ANR does not "see" the existence of a European legal entity such as ERIC. ANR was open to discuss the role of ERICs as transnational legal entities that could facilitate bilateral contracting with national agencies and, thus, serve as interesting and more easily implementable pilots. ANR indicates that it does not exclude the possibility of a meeting with other European research funding agencies organized within the framework of ATMO-ACCESS WP3 but participation in such a meeting must be validated in advance.

IT: The PNIR sets the strategy and co-funding opportunities are encouraged. Projects funded in the framework of PNNR represent an opportunity to fund accesses.

ITINERIS, one of these projects, will build the Italian Hub of Research Infrastructures in the environmental scientific domain for the observation and study of environmental processes in

the atmosphere, marine domain, terrestrial biosphere, and geosphere. ITINERIS will provide access to data and services and will support the Country to address current and expected environmental challenges. ITINERIS coordinates a network of national nodes from 22 RIs (18 from the environmental domain, 2 from agri-food with strong link with the environment and 2 from the PSE domain, supporting services for the marine domain).

A specific workpackage aims to identify, design and implement methodologies, protocols, standards and technological resources to favor access to multidisciplinary services and data which will enable all national environmental RIs to improve their existing work and will represent a strong step forward for the less mature communities by accessing consolidated best-practices. Finally, recommendations and precise guidelines to organise and manage a regular national access programme will be produced and released in support of the national funding agency for the future national access programme.

NO: Good for research projects funded by the Research Council in competitive calls. Operational costs for the use of any research infrastructure are eligible costs in all funding schemes in the Research Council.

PL: There are some competitive ways/paths for financing access to RI, however in most cases such access should be related to research project and should be a part of application for research project financing. In general, it is not well communicated to public and, in my personal opinion, is not well understood by financing agencies themselves as was displayed by the answer provided by the NCN compared to the last call announcement, see point 2b.

RO: Co-funding of the access provision will rely on the in-kind contribution of the RPOs. It may be that in the future there will be national calls but it will take time and sustained efforts to grow this mentality.

SE: There is no long-term stability in the Swedish RI funding system since we operate on 5-year contracts. Securing co-funding from our RPOs is a tedious and never-ending struggle. There are many RIs that compete for RPO support and to achieve the proper prioritization is tough.

UK: If you mean what is the chance of getting national funding to support transnational access from European colleagues to UK laboratory facilities, the answer is no chance. Likewise national funding to support UK scientists wanting to access European facilities. Whether there is an appetite for bilateral agreements with individual countries I don't know, but in the past it's only been considered for major facilities.

Annex 3: Questionnaire for National Funding Agencies and Stakeholders

Explanatory text for national funding agencies and stakeholders

Short summary on ATMO-ACCESS and the aim of this questionnaire

ATMO-ACCESS is a European Commission funded project that aims to deliver a series of recommendations for establishing a comprehensive and sustainable framework for access to distributed atmospheric Research Infrastructures (RI), ensuring integrated access to and optimized use of the services they provide. In practice, ATMO-ACCESS offers physical, remote, virtual or hybrid access to 43 operational European atmospheric research facilities, including ground-based observation stations, simulation chambers, but also mobile facilities and central laboratories that are fundamental elements in distributed RIs.

One of the strategic aims of ATMO-ACCESS is to ensure access to the RIs in the future as well. This needs to be done together with different stakeholders, including partners from the access provision side, such as Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) that operate the national facilities, RI operational structures, such as Calibration and Central Facilities of the RIs that offer calibration services. The stakeholders facilitating the operation of the national facilities include national funding agencies.

The objective of this questionnaire is to initiate national discussion between European RIs offering access to infrastructures and the national funding agencies. The discussion is facilitated by National Contact Persons in direct contact with the representatives of their respective national funding agencies.

The results of the questionnaire are reported as public milestones and deliverables in the ATMO-ACCESS project.

More information about the questionnaire:

Tuukka Petäjä; tuukka.petaja@helsinki.fi

Ulla Wandinger; ulla@tropos.de

Extended explanation of the activity

The aim of this activity is to exchange and share information with the national funding agencies regarding support of National and Transnational access (virtual and physical) to the platforms of distributed research infrastructures.

Research infrastructures (RI) are integrated into the Pillar 1 of the Horizon-Europe programme. They are formed either by "single-site infrastructures" or as distributed infrastructures composed of a set of platforms contributing to the RI. They include data centers and virtual resources to the observational data. The suite of RIs in Europe provide resources and services for the communities of research. The European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) develops policy on pan-European research infrastructures. EU-member countries have developed their own strategies and roadmaps in RIs.

Access to research infrastructures (TNA/VA) for distributed RIs

The investments and operations of RIs are mainly the responsibility of member countries. However, the financing of transnational access and virtual access to distributed RI platforms is funded by European Commission's Infrastructure projects. The TNA/VA Programs make it possible to facilitate access for researchers to research infrastructures by recognizing the eligibility of costs relating to the provision of transnational access to facilities and provision of virtual access to RI data/services. They also develop the attractiveness and therefore the international recognition of these RIs. A sustainable access to infrastructure is therefore a key aspect for scientific innovation and technology development, as well as for economic growth. Today, logical obstacles, financial or administrative borders limit this openness outside of specific EU projects, including, but not limited to, national access and access outside the EU.

ATMO-ACCESS and other access-providing EU-projects

Three projects have been selected as part of a H2020 pilot program. The projects are ATMO-ACCESS, ORP and NFFA-Europe Pilot for a total amount of €30 million (2021-2025):

- ATMO-ACCESS (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/>)
 - Sustainable Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities
 - Integrated into the field of atmospheric sciences, and organized around 3 RIs (IAGOS, ICOS and ACTRIS)
 - Allows the provision of TNA access to 43 platforms (observation sites, atmospheric simulation chambers, calibration centres)
 - One objective is to make proposals to the EC for a sustainable economic model for access for the distributed research infrastructures. The project will make it

possible to engage a reflection with international partners to promote the mutual use of research infrastructures.

- Coordinated by CNRS
- OPTICON-Radionet Pilot, ORP (<https://www.orp-h2020.eu/>)
 - Facilitate astrophysical discoveries with a comprehensive set of Research Infrastructures in the related domains of optical and radio astronomy through supporting a harmonized access procedure, unified data interfaces, and improved services toward scientific excellence
 - Includes 37 research organizations, including all major optical and radio observatories under European responsibility
 - The TNA program provides European astronomers with access to more than 20 astronomical observatories, thus providing access to facilities across the globe terrestrial and over a very wide spectral range (from the optical to the infrared, and to the radio frequencies). This is a rather unique tool that makes ORP the largest IR network in astronomy in the world.
 - Will identify and propose to the European Commission a model economic comparison with the new access of the Commission (reduction of costs in particular), while providing access to the astronomical community.
 - Coordinated by CNRS
- NFFA-Europe Pilot (<https://www.nffa.eu/news/project-updates/pilot-nep/>)
 - Distributed research infrastructure that integrates nanolaboratories (synthesis and manipulation of nanostructures) with analysis tools available at European large-scale facilities, creating a unique offer for the nanosciences and nanomaterials community
 - Coordinated by CNR

Sustainable access to distributed RIs

Via the pilot projects, the Commission showcases elements of future strategy to support TNA/VA access to the distributed RIs. Among the benefits of the access-pilot projects, the commission indicated the following points:

- Harmonization of national and European procedures to provide access in taking into account the access of stakeholders (e.g. authorities public authorities, funding agencies, technology partners, research institutions) from different Member States, associated countries and other countries.

- Propose models, mechanisms or procedures aimed at establishing the optimal conditions for the long-term commitment of funders in order to make sustainable transnational access beyond EU funding.

The projects will contribute to the establishment of a new “European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures” on which the EC is working in partnership with member countries in order to adapt it to the evolution of the IR landscape (green and digital transition, links with the private sector (intellectual property, confidentiality), increased use of the mode of access to distance/hybrid, etc.).

In addition, the commission is evolving its financial mechanisms in Horizon Europe projects via the COFUND tool. As its name suggests, a COFUND program has the particularity of being co-financed by the EC and by the research organizations participating in the project (the share of co-financing being defined according to the projects – typically 30/70 or 20/80). The European Commission plans to extend this tool to the INFRA programme, considering that the responsibility for the financing of the TNA/VA should no longer be entirely on the Commission side.

Questionnaire for national funding agencies and stakeholders

Country:

Funding agency:

National Contact Person:

1) Questions regarding access funding

- a) Do you currently provide financial support for access to research infrastructures?
- b) Do you have bi-lateral access funding opportunities with selected countries? Which countries? How are these decided?
- c) Is there "hidden" support in the funding mechanisms, such as support for mobility that provide financial means for the user? Could the mobility support include costs for the access provider? Would you accept cost statements (xx EUR per access day) from the access provider that would cover the access costs?
- d) Is the support that you offer intended for national or international users?
- e) Would you consider offering financial support for TNA with:
 - i. Co-funding scheme with the European Commission? With which cost-sharing (EU/National: 30% / 70%) or with another ratio? What are the challenges regarding such a funding scheme?
 - ii. Cascade funding? What are the challenges regarding such a funding scheme?
 - iii. Would JPI be a feasible option to support TNA in the future? What are the challenges regarding such a funding scheme? Would "Partnership for Transnational Access", similar to other multi-JPI initiatives be a feasible option?
 - iv. Other funding mechanism?
- f) What are the critical obstacles in different funding schemes?

2) Questions regarding access modalities

Background: *The RIs offer different access modalities:*

- *Physical access: user physically travels to the access offering facility.*
 - *Remote access: users use the services of the facility remotely, e.g., send their own instrument to the facility, installation and operation is done by the staff of the facility.*
 - *Virtual access: user accesses virtual services, such as data.*
 - *Hybrid access: a combination of different access modalities.*
- a) In an ideal case, who would make the decision on accepting TNA application? Do you make the decision regarding the access, or can you delegate the decision?
- b) Is there a preference from the funding agency to support one or the other access modalities?
- c) Is there a difference on how national / international users are treated under different access modalities?

Annex 4: Answers from National Funding Agencies and Stakeholders

1) Questions regarding access funding

a) Do you currently provide financial support for access to research infrastructures?

BG (MES): Not as a dedicated option. Access to RIs is a mandatory component for each of the RIs included in the updated National Roadmap for Research Infrastructure.

FI (Research Council of Finland): Not directly through RI funding, but there is potentially money used for access in Academy Project funding or funding for individual researchers, but this is not systematically followed.

NO (The Research Council of Norway): No, not directly, but Operational costs for the use of any research infrastructure are eligible costs in all funding schemes in the Research Council.

RO (Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization): Yes, but not specific for accessing the RI by users. There is a program aimed at subsidizing national R&D installations but covers only maintenance and operations on daily basis.

SP (Agencia Estatal de Investigación, AEI): The Agencia Estatal de Investigación does not have any instrument to finance direct access to large infrastructures, but this type of action is considered an eligible expense within R&I projects financed through competitive calls.

UK (NERC): Yes.

b) Do you have bi-lateral access funding opportunities with selected countries? Which countries? How are these decided?

BG: N/A

ES: The Agencia Estatal de Investigación does not have any instrument to finance direct access to large infrastructures, but this type of action is considered an eligible expense within R&I projects financed through competitive calls.

FI: No.

NO: No.

RO: There are several bilateral cooperation agreements between Romania and other countries which set the legal framework (at international level). Access to research infrastructures could be decided on the occasion of each call for joint research project proposals.

UK: No.

- c) Is there “hidden” support in the funding mechanisms, such as support for mobility that provide financial means for the user? Could the mobility support include costs for the access provider? Would you accept cost statements (xx EUR per access day) from the access provider that would cover the access costs?

BG: Such option is possible under calls for bilateral projects organised and launched by the National Science Fund (NSF). NSF is a secondary spending unit of the Ministry of Education and Science.

ES: TNA costs are covered are considered as eligibles within the selected R&I projects.

FI: See 1a).

NO: No.

RO: Mobility programs covers travel and subsistence, while the R&D costs (eventually access to R&D facilities) are covered from other programs (e.g. the national R&D program). Not directly (*mobility support to include costs for the access provider*) for the provision of access, but for research activities in which the Romanian institutions are involved. There is no way to do this currently (*to accept cost statements from the access provider*).

UK: Not sure I understand the question, what is meant by mobility in this context?

Yes, there is support mechanisms for access to RI built into our grant funding opportunities. These are typically top sliced from programme/grant budgets and provided directly to the RI that we manage/fund, so not “per access day”.

- d) Is the support that you offer intended for national or international users?

BG: if and where such option could be offered – public funding can cover the cost for national users i.e. Bulgarian scientists and researchers.

ES: No.

FI: -

NO: -

RO: There is no direct support offered for access to infrastructures unless the costs are covered from particular R&D projects.

UK: We don't have funding for this currently and it's unlikely that we could establish new funding mechanisms of any sort for this type of access as a central funder.

e) Would you consider offering financial support for TNA with:

i. Co-funding scheme with the European Commission? With which cost-sharing (EU/National: 30% / 70%) or with another ratio? What are the challenges regarding such a funding scheme?

BG: it is possible, depending on scope, goals, expected results and impact and the benefits for the Bulgarian researchers and research organisations.

ES: No (current position of the AEI).

FI: Not been discussed but worth considering. The one possible challenge is the timing and decision-making process regarding cost-shared funding calls.

NO: No.

RO: *Co-funding scheme with the European Commission?* Only for Romanian participants in various Horizon Europe Partnerships. *With which cost-sharing (EU/National: 30% / 70%) or with another ratio?* According to the rules of the HE Partnership, mainly cash. Several difficulties for in-kind. *What are the challenges regarding such a funding scheme?* Lack of experience in joint-funding (Romania and EU Commission). There are lessons to be learned from both sides. See also comments at point (iii).

UK: -

ii. Cascade funding? What are the challenges regarding such a funding scheme?

BG: Cannot comment or make a statement on this as a general concept/opportunity/option. The approach can be used if and where relevant and appropriate.

ES: No (current position of the AEI).

FI: May be very complicated system but worth considering.

NO: No.

RO: *Cascade funding?* I am not familiar with this scheme. *What are the challenges regarding such a funding scheme?* I don't know, I cannot answer.

UK: -

- iii. Would the JPI (Joint Programming Initiative) be a feasible option to support TNA in the future? What are the challenges regarding such a funding scheme? Would "Partnership for Transnational Access", similar to other multi-JPI initiatives be a feasible option?

BG: Cannot comment or make a statement (will or will not) on this as a general concept/opportunity/option. It could be.

ES: No (current position of the AEI).

FI: Not been discussed but worth considering. Partnerships are laborious systems and creating one requires long process.

NO: No.

RO: *Would the JPI (Joint Programming Initiative) be a feasible option to support TNA in the future?* Yes, if is based on clear and equitable principles. Currently, Romania participates to several JPIs like: OCEAN, HDHL, FACE, but none of them involve research infrastructures as such. *What are the challenges regarding such a funding scheme?* Coordination, bureaucracy, transparency. When it comes to large research infrastructures, the coordination of an agile program can be very difficult, creates too much bureaucracy and generally is not transparent enough. Putting resources in a common pot must be seconded by a decision-making mechanism which allows the participants to have control on how the resources are planned, distributed, and spent. As long as the resources for funding the TNA come also from the provider and/or the national funding agency, these actors must be involved in the decision-making across the whole selection process. *Would "Partnership for Transnational Access", similar to other multi-JPI initiatives be a feasible option?* Yes, with the concerns written above.

UK: -

- iv. Other funding mechanism?

BG: -

ES: -

FI: -

NO: No.

RO: -

UK: -

f) What are the critical obstacles in different funding schemes?

BG: Cannot comment or make a statement as a respond to such question – this would require a country case study. To comment on difficulties - Demarcation (of the cope and coverage of various funding instruments and schemes) is a challenge.

ES: Currently, the AEI only finances R&D projects through competitive calls. In the event that it is considered that the project requires the use of infrastructure for its execution, the access and associated expenses will be eligible and covered.

FI: How to streamline the projects selected via European Commission evaluation system with the national FIRI roadmap?

NO: -

RO: Costs and decision-making.

UK: Available money and mechanisms for funding overseas researchers.

3) Questions regarding access modalities

Background: *The RIs offer different access modalities:*

- *Physical access: user physically travels to the access offering facility.*
- *Remote access: users use the services of the facility remotely, e.g., send their own instrument to the facility, installation and operation is done by the staff of the facility.*
- *Virtual access: user accesses virtual services, such as data.*
- *Hybrid access: a combination of different access modalities.*

a) In an ideal case, who would make the decision on accepting TNA application? Do you make the decision regarding the access, or can you delegate the decision?

BG: this matter is managed by the RI.

ES: -

FI: RI internal process.

NO: The Research Council has no calls for funding access to RIs.

RO: The institution providing access (possibly advised by a panel of experts). The responsibility to efficiently spend the allocated resources is on the institution providing access, therefore the provider must also have the possibility to decide. Of course, the provider will have to inform and report to the funding agency (whoever it may be), which ultimately decides to continue or

not the allocation of funds. In an ideal case, the Ministry shall not be involved in the day-to-day decisions (e.g. selection of the access projects), but should give this mandate to the institutions which provide access. The Ministry should be involved in deciding regularly (e.g. once per year or every two years) if resources should continue to be allocated to the corresponding institutions, and how much.

UK: Individual RI operators.

b) Is there a preference from the funding agency to support one or the other access modalities?

BG: N/A.

ES: -

FI: No.

NO: N/A.

RO: I personally don't understand why virtual access (access to data) should be supported since data is open and the Data Centres are already funded by each infrastructure. For the other 2 modalities (physical and remote), and combination of those, I have no objections. Of course, physical access should be organized only when is not possible to solve the scope of the project through remote access. This is to limit unnecessary travel and the associated costs, both financial and environmental.

UK: No. It would depend on the RI in question and what was appropriate.

c) Would it be possible to support national, European and international users? Is there a difference on how national / international users are treated under different access modalities?

BG: With regards to public funds – national/Bulgarian users could be financed. Bilateral projects (under bilateral agreements) could finance and allow for access which is by default decided/granted by the respective RI.

ES: -

FI: -

NO: N/A.

RO: Yes, based on merits. A public call should be launched and evaluators should be independent experts to advise the access provider on the opportunity and impact of the project. *Is there a difference on how national / international users are treated under different access modalities?* No. Transparency, merits and efficient use of (public) funds are to be used.

UK: Direct funding would currently only be possible for UK based researchers.

- d) From the funding agency point of view, are the differences or preferences supporting access to different user groups, such as scientists, private sector (e.g., instrument manufacturers), public sector (e.g., city air quality authorities)?

BG: No, there aren't. MES BG does not influence RIs decisions on this matter. Any project that bears tangible benefits for science and society is worthy of consideration regardless of the type of organization that runs it.

ES: -

FI: No, but must be based on scientific excellence from the Research Council of Finland perspective. If you ask from the Business Finland, they might prefer business users, but they do not support any RESEARCH infrastructures as such, but higher TRL level technology infrastructures.

NO: N/A.

RO: No, all are important, and the "share" depends on the specific of each research infrastructure and facility. We cannot decide top-down based on artificial criteria. Some facilities are more science-oriented, some more technology-oriented, some more service-oriented. The variety of access provision ensures higher impact. This is why the provider, who knows best its capacity and users, is the one who should decide where the allocated resources are best placed. Of course, an overall planning and monitoring at the level of research infrastructures and funding agencies is necessary, but the micro-management should be avoided.

UK: If we were to fund it directly then it would be restricted to eligible organisations, typically research organisations and not in the private sector.

- e) What would be the key features of the access to get financial support? Such as scientific breakthrough, business potential generated by the access (proof-of-concept, benchmarking new innovative observations), education and training of visitors.

BG: Measurable benefits for science and society, benefits for Bulgarian scientists (knowledge and skills), benefits for industry and economy.

ES: -

FI: See above.

NO: N/A.

RO: In my opinion the key feature is societal impact, even if indirect (as in the case of atmospheric research infrastructures). Research infrastructures are more than a collection of single access providers; therefore they should seek to exploit the uniqueness of their collective capacity. They should serve with priority actors which can multiply and diversify the impact, such as international organizations, research networks, instrument and added-value service developers, policy makers, etc. Scientific and technological advancements should remain the main goal of the access projects, potentially including aspects related to education and training.

UK: Any funding for access would be tied to an active eligible research activity undertaken by an eligible organisation (see above).

4) Additional input in free text

NO: The Research Council of Norway does not fund access to any research infrastructure directly, but Operational costs for the use of any research infrastructure are eligible costs in all funding schemes in the Research Council.

UK: These answers represent my own opinion and understanding and may not be reflective of ongoing policy development I am not aware of currently.

